

A Great Journey along Industrial Data Science

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Abstract: S. Joe Qin is the Fluor Professor at the Viterbi School of Engineering at the University of Southern California. He is an IEEE Fellow, IFAC Fellow, and AIChE Fellow. Dr. Qin's research interests include data analytics, machine learning, process monitoring and fault diagnosis, model predictive control, system identification, semiconductor manufacturing and control, building energy optimization, and predictive maintenance and are in parts closely related to the work of Nina Thornhill. He has published over 400 international journal papers, book chapters conference papers and presentations, delivered over 50 invited plenary or keynote speeches and over 120 invited technical seminars worldwide.

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The first time I got acquainted with Prof. Nina Thornhill was about mid-1990, when the boom in artificial neural networks in process engineering had seen its promises and limitations. It was also the time when I was beginning my academic career at the University of Texas at Austin from a prior industrial position at Emerson Process Management. I was able to develop a neural network software product for Emerson to do inferential sensors for process properties, known as Intelligent Sensor Toolkit.

Aside from inferential sensor applications, other promises of neural networks in process systems did not pan out. Nevertheless, as a junior professor I had to pick a research direction that could go a long way. From my Ph.D. thesis work I believed that multivariate statistics along with neural networks could provide a solid foundation for data-driven process applications.

To look back at the process control history one cannot overlook the impact of one individual, who is Dr. David Smith, manager of process control at Dupont. David, along with Drs. Tunde Ogunnaike, Mike Piovoso and others, made Dupont the world leader in implementing model predictive control, plant wide control and data analytics for industrial practice. David also provided post-doc positions for people like Frank Doyle, Richard Braatz, Jay Lee, and Mike Henson, who are current leaders in process control research and education.

I was fortunate to have received a Dupont Young Faculty Award as an assistant professor, so I sought advice from David on what problems I could focus on in research. David simply said to me: you should really pay attention to Nina Thornhill's work in lossless data compression. I knew very well from my industrial experience that the data compression practice was a roadblock in making data analytics effective. This was the beginning of my acquaintance of Nina and her

exceptional career in identifying impactful problems and providing solutions of data analytics in process engineering.

Nina's journey in process control over 35 years can be clearly attributed to industrial data analytics. From the early stage between 1985 and 1995, Nina focused almost exclusively on fermentation process control. Since 1996 her focus has shifted to data compression and process monitoring. Some of her contributions are well summarized in *The impact of compression on data-driven process analyses*, NF Thornhill, MAAS Choudhury, SL Shah, Journal of Process Control 14 (4), 389-398, 2004. Her contribution in the use of principal component analysis for process analytics can be represented in Spectral principal component analysis of dynamic process data, NF Thornhill, SL Shah, B Huang, A Vishnubhotla, Control Engineering Practice 10 (8), 833-846, 2002. These works documented her collaboration with the process control group at University of Alberta.

It is perhaps fair to say that Nina's most impactful contribution is in control performance analysis, as highlighted in the following papers:

1. On **detection and diagnosis of valve stiction in control loops**, Detection and diagnosis of oscillation in control loops, NF Thornhill, T Hägglund, *Control Engineering Practice* 5 (10), 1343-1354, 1997, and Refinery-wide control loop performance assessment, NF Thornhill, M Oettinger, P Fedenczuk, *Journal of Process Control* 9 (2), 109-124, 1999
2. On **detection and diagnosis of plant-wide oscillations**, Detection of multiple oscillations in control loops, NF Thornhill, B Huang, H Zhang, *Journal of Process control* 13 (1), 91-100, 2003, and Diagnosis of plant-wide oscillation through data-driven analysis and process understanding, NF

Thornhill, JW Cox, MA Paulonis, Control Engineering Practice 11 (12), 1481-1490, 2003

3. On **finding disturbance propagation directions**, Finding the direction of disturbance propagation in a chemical process using transfer entropy, M Bauer, JW Cox, MH Caveness, JJ Downs, NF Thornhill, IEEE transactions on control systems technology 15 (1), 12-21, 2006, and A practical method for identifying the propagation path of plant-wide disturbances, M Bauer, NF Thornhill, Journal of Process Control 18 (7-8), 707-719, 2008, and
4. A review paper, **Advances and new directions in plant-wide disturbance detection and diagnosis**, NF Thornhill, A Horch, Control Engineering Practice 15 (10), 1196-1206, 2007

It is not difficult to see from these works that Nina was able to collaborate with the right people on the right topics, particularly the Tennessee Eastman process control group led by James Downs, where she identified a great control problem of sustained plant-wide oscillations. Her works also provided insightful and skilful applications of frequency data analytics as a solution. This collaborative work served as an inspiration to several of my own contributions in causality analysis and dynamic component analysis.

In the recent ten years Nina's work included **cause and effect analysis of chemical processes**, as shown in Cause-and-effect analysis in chemical processes utilizing XML, plant connectivity and quantitative process history, J Thambirajah,

L Benabbas, M Bauer, NF Thornhill, Computers & Chemical Engineering 33 (2), 503-512, 2009, and **analysis of alarm systems**, in A combined analysis of plant connectivity and alarm logs to reduce the number of alerts in an automation system, M Schlegel, L Christiansen, NF Thornhill, A Fay, Journal of process control 23 (6), 839-851, 2013.

One of Nina's most recent works is on **energy systems and demand side management** from around 2010. She demonstrated the importance of stability monitoring in electrical power systems in Comparison of three electromechanical oscillation damping estimation methods, Jukka Turunen, Jegatheeswaran Thambirajah, Mats Larsson, Bikash C Pal, Nina F Thornhill, Liisa C Haarla, William W Hung, Alex M Carter, Tuomas Rauhala, IEEE Transactions on power systems 26 (4), 2398-2407, 2011, and A dynamic mode decomposition framework for global power system oscillation analysis, E Barocio, BC Pal, NF Thornhill, AR Messina, IEEE Transactions on Power Systems 30 (6), 2902-2912, 2014. These works are certainly relevant to her expertise in the understanding of oscillations in chemical plants.

Last, but not least, in the new era of big data and data science, Nina has turned to a promising application of data science, that is **predictive maintenance**, as shown in Operational optimization of compressors in parallel considering condition-based maintenance, DP Xenos, GM Kopanos, M Ciccotti, EN Pistikopoulos, NF Thornhill, Computer Aided Chemical Engineering 33, 1213-1218, 2014.